

THE INCREMENTAL DAMAGE THEORY OF PARTICULATE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH A DUCTILE INTERPHASE

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1 Introduction

Particulate-reinforced composites (PRCs) are becoming more and more attractive in the modern industry. Many properties of PRCs are influenced by particle size, which attributes to the significant modification of microstructures by the introduction of inorganic particles. In explaining particle size effect, the interphase is undoubtedly one of the most important factors [1]. Quite a number of researches have been published to date for studying the impact of the interphase, and the readers can refer our previous work [2]. Jiang et al. have systematically investigated the effects of the interphase on the stiffness, elastic–plastic and damage behaviors of PRCs by using FEM, theoretical and experimental methods [2-3]. The elastic–plastic deformation of an interphase was found to have a great influence on the mechanical behavior of PRCs. Ruiz-Navas et al. [4] found that Al+Ti₅Si₃-Cu composites exhibit the superior mechanical properties as compared to Al+Ti₅Si₃ composites. Lauke [5] numerically analyzed the interfacial adhesion strength between a coated particle and a polymer matrix material, and indicated the influence of a ductile interphase on the local stress field. Wang and Yang [6] have employed FEM analysis to simulate the behavior of energy dissipation for the PRCs with a ductile interphase. For the PRCs, Tohgo and Chou [7] and Tohgo and Weng [8] proposed an ID theory of PRCs taking into account the plasticity of a matrix and progressive debonding damage of particles based on Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method and Mori–Tanaka's mean field concept. In order to fully study the effect of an interphase, it is necessary to extend Tohgo's ID theory to the three–phase case with a ductile interphase.

Based on the previous studies [2-3], a ductile interphase was introduced and studied in the frame of ID theory [7]. Numerical computations of the stress–strain relations under uniaxial tension were carried out for different microstructures. Influences of debonding, interphase properties, particle size and

particle volume fraction on the overall stress–strain response of PRCs were studied systematically. Also, a unit-cell (UC) based FEM was performed.

2 Incremental damage theory of PRC with a ductile interphase

The adopted composite system consists of three phases of particle, matrix and interphase between them. The interphase concentration f_i is related to that of particles f_p by

$$f_i/f_p = (1 + 2t/d_p)^3 - 1 \quad (1)$$

here, d_p and t are particle diameter and interphase thickness, respectively. f_{p0} is the initial content of particles, and the initial loading of the interphase is determined by Eqn. (1).

2.1 Constitutive relations of the constituents

The elastic incremental stress–strain relations of the constituents follow as:

$$d\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i \neq \mathbf{C}_i(E_i, \nu_i) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^i, \quad i = M, I \text{ or } P \quad (2)$$

where, the symbol “:” is contraction product, $d\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i$ and $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^i$ are the incremental stress and strain, respectively, and $\mathbf{C}_i(E_i, \nu_i)$ is the stiffness tensor. E_i and ν_i are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratios of constituents, respectively. The plastic deformations of the constituents are described by the Prandtl–Reuss equation (the J_2 -flow theory) as,

$$d\boldsymbol{\sigma}^i = \mathbf{C}_i(E_i', \nu_i') : d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^i, \quad i = M, I \text{ or } P \quad (3)$$

where

$$E_i' = \frac{E_i}{1 + E_i/H_i'}, \quad \nu_i' = \frac{\nu_i + E_i/(2H_i')}{1 + E_i/H_i'}$$

E_i' and ν_i' represent tangent Young's moduli and tangent Poisson's ratios of the constituents under elastic-plastic deformation. H_i' shows the work-hardening ratio of each phase,

$$H_i' = d\sigma_e^i / (d\varepsilon_e^{pl})^i$$

$$\sigma_e^i = \sqrt{3/2(\sigma'_{kl})^i(\sigma'_{kl})^i}$$

$$(d\varepsilon_e^{pl})^i = \sqrt{2/3(d\varepsilon_{kl}^{pl})^i(d\varepsilon_{kl}^{pl})^i}$$

Here, σ_e^i and $(d\varepsilon_e^{pl})^i$ are the von Mises equivalent stress and incremental equivalent plastic strain, respectively. $(\sigma'_{kl})^i$ the deviatoric stress component, and $(d\varepsilon_{kl}^{pl})^i$ the incremental plastic strain. Eqn. (3) is strictly valid in the case of monotonic proportional loading. In the composite system, the stress and strain of particles, interphase and matrix are denoted with superscripts "P", "I" and "M", respectively, and without any superscripts for the composite.

2.2 Incremental damage theory with a ductile interphase

Fig. 1 The states of composite undergoing damage process before and after incremental deformation, df_P is a volume fraction of the reinforcements damaged in the incremental deformation.

Fig. 1 shows the states before and after an incremental deformation of a representative volume element during the damage process, where a constant macroscopic stress σ and its increment $d\sigma$ are applied on the boundary of RVE. All the debonding damage is supposed to occur between particle and interphase. The states before the incremental deformation are described in terms of the intact particle content f_P and damaged particle content f_P^d . The initial damaged particle content $f_P^d = 0$, and $f_P = f_{P0}$. df_P denotes the content of particles debonded in an incremental deformation. The states after the deformation can be expressed by the intact particles loading $f_P - df_P$ and damaged particles loading $f_P^d + df_P$. Some necessary assumptions are firstly given:

- (1) All the constituents and composites are isotropic.
- (2) The debonding damage is controlled by the critical stress of particles.
- (3) After the damage, particle stress reduces to zero.

- (4) The progressive damage is described by a decrease in the intact particle content and an increase in the debonded particle concentration.

The constitutive equations of an isotropic PRC are expressed in the form of the hydrostatic $(d\varepsilon_{kk} - d\sigma_{kk})$ and deviatoric parts $(d\varepsilon'_{ij} - d\sigma'_{ij})$. So, the incremental strain $d\varepsilon$ ($d\varepsilon_{kk}$, $d\varepsilon'_{ij}$)–stress $d\sigma$ ($d\sigma_{kk}$, $d\sigma'_{ij}$) relation of the composite is given by,

$$d\varepsilon_{kk} = \frac{1}{3\kappa_t} d_{kk} + \frac{1}{3\kappa_d} d_{kk}^P df_P,$$

$$d\varepsilon'_{ij} = \frac{1}{2\mu_t} d'_{ij} + \frac{1}{2\mu_d} d'_{ij}^P df_P \quad (4)$$

where

$$\kappa_t = \kappa_{Mk} [1 - \gamma / (1 + \alpha \gamma)]$$

$$\kappa_d = \kappa_{Mk} (1 - \alpha) [1 - (1 - \alpha) \gamma]$$

$$\mu_t = \mu_{Mk} [1 - \gamma / (1 + \beta \gamma)]$$

$$\mu_d = \mu_{Mk} (1 - \beta) [1 - (1 - \beta) \gamma]$$

and

$$\gamma_\kappa = -\frac{f_P (\kappa_P - \kappa_m)}{\kappa_m + (\kappa_P - \kappa_m) \alpha} - \frac{f_{I0} (\kappa_I - \kappa_m)}{\kappa_M + (\kappa_I - \kappa_m) \alpha} + \frac{f_P^d}{(1 - \alpha)}$$

$$\gamma_\mu = -\frac{f_P (\mu_P - \mu_m)}{\mu_m + (\mu_P - \mu_m) \beta} - \frac{f_{I0} (\mu_I - \mu_m)}{\mu_m + (\mu_I - \mu_m) \beta} + \frac{f_P^d}{(1 - \beta)}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{3} \frac{1 + \nu_M}{1 - \nu_M}, \quad \beta = \frac{2}{15} \frac{4 - 5\nu_M}{1 - \nu_M}$$

Here, κ_i and μ_i are bulk and shear modulus of three constituents, respectively, which are related to Young's modulus E_i and Poisson's ratio ν_i by

$$\kappa_i = \frac{E_i}{3(1 - 2\nu_i)}, \quad \mu_i = \frac{E_i}{2(1 + \nu_i)} \quad (5)$$

The incremental stresses of the three phases $d\sigma^P$, $d\sigma^M$ and $d\sigma^I$ are expressed by

$$d\sigma_{kk}^P = \frac{\kappa_P (d\sigma)_{kk} + \kappa_P^P df_P}{[1 - (1 - \alpha) \gamma_\kappa] [\kappa_P + (\kappa_m - \kappa_P) \alpha]}$$

$$d\sigma_{ij}^{Pp} = \frac{\mu_P (d\sigma)_{ij} + \mu_P^P df_P}{[1 - (1 - \beta) \gamma_\mu] [\mu_P + (\mu_m - \mu_P) \beta]}$$

$$d\sigma_{kk}^M = \frac{1}{1 - (1 - \alpha) \gamma_\kappa} d_{kk} + d_{kk}^P df_P$$

$$d\sigma_{ij}^{Mp} = \frac{1}{1 - (1 - \beta) \gamma_\mu} d'_{ij} + d'_{ij}^P df_P$$

$$d\sigma_{kk}^I = \frac{\kappa_I (d\sigma)_{kk} + \kappa_I^P df_P}{[1 - (1 - \alpha) \gamma_\kappa] [\kappa_I + (\kappa_m - \kappa_I) \alpha]}$$

$$d\sigma_{ij}^{Ip} = \frac{\mu_I (d\sigma)_{ij} + \mu_I^P df_P}{[1 - (1 - \beta) \gamma_\mu] [\mu_I + (\mu_m - \mu_I) \beta]} \quad (6)$$

2.3 The critical stress of debonding damage

The particle encounters debonding damage when the microscopic stress of particle reaches a critical value σ_{cr}^p as

$$\sigma_{cr}^p = K_C / \sqrt{d_p} \quad (7)$$

Γ or K_C is uniquely given for a combination of constituent materials in composites, and they would be basically obtained by fracture toughness tests for the interface between constituent materials. Eqn. (7) describes the dependence of the critical stress on particle size.

2.4 Equivalent stress of the constituents

Fig. 2 The stress–strain relation of PRC is classified into three pieces I, II and III.

The equivalent stress can be used to indicate the elastic-plastic state of a ductile material, and Tohgo et al. determined the equivalent stress of the matrix by the energy method in the ID theory. For the present problem, the equivalent stresses of two phases need to be given simultaneously, and unfortunately they combined in the same equation. So, field fluctuation (FF) method [9] should be adopted here to solve this dilemma. As known from the previous study [2], the microstructure under study will experience three stages during the damage progression. They are the composite, debonding and porous material, respectively. Therefore, the uniaxial stress–strain relation of a composite shown in Fig. 2 can be classified into I, II and III stages. “I” represents the composites, “II” the debonding process and “III” the porous material. The equivalent stresses of the matrix and interphase are separately determined in the three stages.

For the first stage, the composite contains particles, matrix and interphase. An initial equivalent stress σ_e^r ($r=I, M$) of the constituents before plastic deformation and damage is given by

$$(\sigma_e^r)^2 = \frac{3\alpha_r^2}{f_r E^2} \frac{\delta E}{\delta \mu_r}, \quad r = I, M$$

and their increments are given by

$$d\sigma_e^r(\sigma_e^r) = \frac{3\mu_r^2}{f_r \sigma_e^r E^2} \frac{\delta E}{\delta \mu_r} \quad r = I, M$$

For the third stage, the composite reduces to a porous material, and contains voids, matrix and interphase. The increments of the equivalent stress can be also determined by the above formula, but the overall modulus E must reduce to a porous material.

For the second stage, the composite contains voids, particles, matrix and interphase, and the boundary conditions continuously changes since the stress incrementally decreases induced by the debonding damage. Therefore, the prerequisite to use field fluctuation method does not strictly hold. According to Tohgo’s energy method [8], the combined energy equation is given as,

$$dU - dR = \frac{f_M E'_M}{6(1+\nu'_M)} \sigma_e^M d\sigma_e^M + \frac{f_I E'_I}{6(1+\nu'_I)} \sigma_e^I d\sigma_e^I + \frac{f_M}{\kappa_M} \sigma_m^M d\sigma_m^M + \frac{f_I}{\kappa_I} \sigma_m^I d\sigma_m^I + f_P \sigma^P d\epsilon^P - \frac{1}{2} df_P \sigma^P \epsilon^P \quad (8)$$

where, σ_m^i ($i=M, I$) denotes the hydrostatic stress of the constituents, dU is the incremental energy of composites and dR is the energy released by debonding damage

$$dU = \sigma d\epsilon, \quad dR = \frac{1}{2} \sigma d\epsilon^d \quad (9)$$

Following Qiu and Weng’s definition [10] of the equivalent stress,

$$\begin{aligned} (\sigma_e^{(r)})^2 &= \frac{1}{V_r} \int_{V_r} \frac{3}{2} \sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}) \sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}) dV \\ (\sigma_e^{(r)} + d\sigma_e^{(r)})^2 &= \frac{1}{V_r} \int_{V_r} \frac{3}{2} (\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}) + d\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x})) \\ &\quad (\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}) + d\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x})) dV, \quad r = I, M \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Neglecting the higher order terms of the increments, one obtains

$$\sigma_e^{(r)} d\sigma_e^{(r)} = \frac{3}{2} \left(\sigma_{ij}^{(r)} d\sigma_{ij}^{(r)} + \frac{1}{f_r} \int_{V_r} \frac{3}{2} \sigma_{ij}^{pt(r)} d\sigma_{ij}^{pt(r)} dV \right) \quad (11)$$

where, $\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}$ is the average deviatoric stress of the r -th phase, which is defined by Eqn. (10). It is very difficult to know the distribution of $\sigma_{ij}^{pt(r)}$ in the materials. An approximation method is adopted here, and a ratio ζ is defined by

$$\zeta = d\sigma_{ij}^{pt} / d\sigma_e^M$$

$$d\sigma_e^{(r)} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(\sigma_{ij}^{(r)} + d\sigma_{ij}^{(r)})(\sigma_{ij}^{(r)} + d\sigma_{ij}^{(r)})} - \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}} \quad (12)$$

Based on the above relation, the equivalent stresses of the ductile constituents can be solved. Since the detailed microscopic stress $\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x})$ in the composites fluctuates over its mean value defined by Eqn. (10), the above equation shows that the perturbed stress fields $\sigma_{ij}^{(r)}(\mathbf{x})$ over the constituents should change with the same ratio as the average stresses. This strategy partially accounts for the fluctuation effect by the inhomogeneity from Eqn. (12), and the following equation is reached,

$$d\sigma_e^M = \frac{\Psi}{\left(\frac{f_M E'_M}{6(1+\nu'_M)} \sigma_{ij}^M + \frac{f_I E'_I}{6(1+\nu'_I)} \sigma_{ij}^I \right)} \quad (13)$$

$$\Psi = dU - dR + \frac{1}{2} df_p \sigma^p \epsilon^p - \frac{f_M}{K_M} \sigma_{ij}^M d_m^M$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^M = \frac{f_I}{K_I} \sigma_{ij}^I - f_p \sigma^p \epsilon^p$$

3 FEM

The behavior of PRC is examined by using a unit-cell with the assumption of a periodical microstructure. The computation model shown in Fig. 3 is an approximation of a periodical distribution of three-dimensional hexagonal cells, here, $d_p=30\mu\text{m}$, $t=1.5\mu\text{m}$ and $f_{p0}=6.3\%$. Only 1/4 of a RVE is used in the simulation by considering the symmetry conditions. Periodical boundary conditions are imposed on the RVE as,

$$u_z=0 \text{ along the axis } z=0$$

$$u_r=0 \text{ along the axis } r=0$$

$$z=A \text{ along the axis } z=U$$

where, u_z and u_r are displacements along the directions z and r , respectively. On the upper boundary ($z=U$) a uniform displacement U was prescribed in z -direction.

Fig. 3 FE mesh and 2D problem, $d_p=30\mu\text{m}$, $t=1.5\mu\text{m}$ and $f_{p0}=6.3\%$.

FE mesh of an axisymmetric RVE is shown in Fig. 3. A perfect bonding is assumed between three phases. Element size was checked so that numeric results are independent on the mesh density.

4 Results and discussions

The stress (σ_{xx}) and strain (ϵ_{xx}) in the tensile direction of the SiC particle reinforced aluminum (Al) alloy composite (SiC/A356-T4) under uniaxial tension was studied [11]. The stress–strain relation of Al-alloy matrix is given by Ramberg–Osgood relation as:

$$\epsilon_e^M = \frac{\sigma_e^M}{E_M} + \lambda \frac{\sigma_y}{E_M} \left(\frac{\sigma_e^M}{\sigma_y} \right)^{1/n} \quad (14)$$

Where, E_M is the Young's modulus, σ_y is the yield strength, n is the strain hardening exponent, and λ is a constant. $E_M=70\text{GPa}$, $\nu_M=0.33$, $\sigma_y=86\text{MPa}$, $n=0.212$, $\lambda=3/7$, $E_p=427\text{GPa}$, $\nu_p=0.17$, $E_I=250\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_I=0.33$. The stress–strain relation of the ductile interphase also obeys the formula of Eqn. (14), only σ_y and n are changed. $K_C=2.6 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ [2] was used for interfacial debonding.

4.1 Analytical model

4.1.1 FF method and ID theory

Fig. 4 Comparison between the stress–strain relations of the composite, porous material and debonding with an interphase by FF method and ID theory.

In our previous work [2], the accuracy of ID theory has been already confirmed through the comparison with the experiments. The FF method in obtaining the equivalent stress needs to be verified firstly by comparing with the ID theory. Fig. 4 shows the comparison between the stress–strain relations of a composite, debonding process and porous material with an interphase predicted by FF method and ID theory. Since the plastic behavior of a ductile interphase couldn't be considered with the ID theory, a brittle interphase was assumed in the numerical computation. As clearly seen from the comparison, all the results predicted by FF method are in good agreement with those by ID theory.

4.1.2 Role of particle size

Fig. 5 demonstrates the particle size effects on the stress–strain relations of the composites with no damage. The ID denotes Tohgo–Chou–Weng's model without particle size effects. Here, two cases with a brittle and ductile interphase were studied for the direct comparison, and the interphase thickness is supposed to be 2.5 μm. The overall stresses of the composite with a ductile interphase are remarkably lower than those with a brittle one, which is caused by the decrease of stress transfer capacity in due to the yielding deformation of a ductile interphase. As the particle size is larger than 30 μm, the stress–strain curves converge to a conventional result by the ID theory without particle size effects. However, as the particle size is smaller than 15 μm, the stress–strain relations become size-dependent evidently.

Fig. 5 Particle size effects on the stress–strain relations of the composites.

Fig. 6 Particle size effect on the stress–strain relations of the composites with debonding damage.

Fig. 6 shows the effect of particle size on the stress–strain relations of the composites with debonding damage. After the debonding damage, the stress–strain relation of the composite is almost consistent with a porous material. The debonding damage is delayed much more with smaller particle size, which is easily explained from Eqn. (7).

4.1.3 Role of interphase plasticity

Fig. 7 Dependence of the stress–strain relations of composites on the yield strength of an interphase with a constant thickness with debonding damage.

Fig. 7 shows the dependence of the stress–strain relations of the composites on the yield strength of an interphase with a given thickness without debonding damage. The higher the ratio σ_y^I/σ_y^M is, the earlier the particle detaches from the matrix. Since the interphase with higher yielding strength transfers the applied load to the reinforcements more efficiently, the particle stress would increase up to the critical stress more rapidly. In summary, the yield strength of an interphase significantly influences the damage process and deformation behavior of the composites.

4.1.4 Verification of analytical model

Comparisons will be conducted between Lloyd's experiments [11] and numerical results. Number

frequency of particles was assumed to follow the lognormal distribution,

$$p(d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\delta d} \exp\left[-\frac{(\ln d - \phi)^2}{2\delta^2}\right] \quad (15)$$

where, δ is the standard deviation and the mean particle diameter \bar{d}_p is given by

$$\bar{d}_p = \exp(\phi + \delta^2/2) \quad (16)$$

In Eqn. (15), δ and ϕ were set as 0.4 and 2.693, respectively. Fig. 8 shows the comparison of the stress–strain relations between the predictions and the testing results, and progress of debonding damage represented by void volume fraction f_p^d as well. Here, the average particle size is 16 μm , and the interphase thickness was assumed to be 1.5 μm . It is found that the experimental results can be well described by the present model.

Fig. 8 Comparison of stress–strain relations between the predictions and Lloyd’s testing results

4.2 FE analysis

4.2.1 Stress transfer

Fig. 9 Stress distribution in the axisymmetric RVE subjected to tensile loading (loading direction \uparrow).

Fig. 10 Plastic strain distribution in the axisymmetric RVE subjected to tensile loading (loading direction \uparrow): (a) $\sigma_y^I = 5\sigma_y^M$ and (b) $\sigma_y^I = 0.5\sigma_y^M$.

Fig. 9 depicts the stress distribution in the axisymmetric RVE subjected to tension: (a) $\sigma_y^I = 5\sigma_y^M$ and (b) $\sigma_y^I = 0.5\sigma_y^M$. The particle stress shown in Fig. 9b is lower relative to that in Fig. 9a for high yield strength. So, an interphase with higher yield strength is much more efficient in increasing the stress transfer in the particle. The present results are also helpful to explain the variation tendency of stress–strain relation shown in Fig. 8. An interphase with higher yielding stress could transfer higher stress to the particle, so the particle stress become much higher, and reach up to the σ_{cr}^p earlier.

4.2.2 Yield initiation

The yielding strength of a ductile interphase is expected to change yield initiation in the composites. Fig. 10 illustrates the plastic strain distribution in the axisymmetric RVE with different interphase. For a stronger interphase with $\sigma_y^I = 5\sigma_y^M$ (Fig. 10a), the matrix firstly yields in which a certain distance far from the particle pole and along the angle of 45° . However, for a weak interphase shown in Fig. 10b, interphase yielding would start at 45° , and plastic strain magnitude is lower. These results also agree with those published in [6].

5 Conclusions

A ductile interphase was considered in the frame of incremental damage theory to study the elastic–plastic–damage behavior of the composites. Based on the present model, influences of progressive debonding damage, particle size and interphase properties on the overall stress–strain response of PRC were discussed. Moreover, FEM was used to understand the role of the interphase.

- (1) The particle size effect on the elastic–plastic–damage behavior of the composites is explained from the viewpoint of a ductile interphase.
- (2) For the composites with a ductile interphase, the equivalent stresses of the ductile constituents can be determined by field fluctuation method.
- (3) The material properties of the ductile interphase do have a great effect on the overall mechanical behaviors and damage propagation of the composites.

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